

Wrap-up of DECam at 10 Years: Looking Back, Looking Forward Workshop

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Over 80 scientists met in Tucson on 12–14 September 2022 to celebrate 10 years of operation of the Dark Energy Camera (DECam), to present scientific projects old and new, and to discuss future instrumentation possibilities for the [Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope](#) at CTIO as well as the [Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope](#) at KPNO, given their tight coordination and synergies.

In a remarkable coincidence, the milestone of [one million images](#) since the commissioning began was reached on the afternoon of 12 September, the first day of the meeting.

DECam, sited at the prime focus of the Blanco, is the widest-field big-telescope CCD imager until the Simonyi Survey Telescope at [Vera C. Rubin Observatory](#) begins operations.

DECam was built to carry out the Dark Energy Survey (DES), a project aimed at estimating the equation of state for dark energy by mapping the galaxy distribution over a wide range of redshifts. DES used 592.5 nights on the telescope, primarily scheduled in the B semesters, to carry out a five-band imaging survey of 5000 square degrees of the South Galactic Cap together with a survey covering 30 square degrees to discover and follow up on [Type Ia supernovae](#).

While DES concluded in 2019, the analysis of all six years of data is still underway, and the final cosmological results are expected in 2024. So far the results confirm the Λ CDM cosmology to tighter limits than previously, but there are hints — for example from a smoother matter distribution than expected — that non-standard physics may be required

Group photo from DECam at 10 Years workshop. Credit: P. Marenfeld (NOIRLab).

for a full explanation of the results. DES itself enabled several other major investigations, of which perhaps the most important has been the discovery of many small dwarf spheroidal galaxies that are companions of our Milky Way and the Magellanic Clouds. These discoveries, and the associated follow-ups with DECam and other telescopes, also provide stringent tests of dark matter.

When not taking data for DES, DECam was used for community and Chilean projects, many of which are major surveys in themselves. For instance, the [DECam Legacy Survey \(DECaLS\)](#) covered the sky around the celestial equator from declination -23°S to $+33^{\circ}\text{N}$ in the g, i, z bands to identify [targets for DESI](#). The range of science covered by community use of DECam ranges from Solar System asteroids to Lyman-alpha emitting galaxies forming at the dawn of the Universe, and everything in between.

DECam is more than ever a highly relevant instrument, and in the last few years, its capability has been extended with several community-purchased narrow- and medium-band

filters. Results from projects with these filters [were presented at the meeting](#), and the announcement that a new filter to be used for searching for very metal-poor stars had been successfully fabricated was enthusiastically received.

DECam is expected to be an important player in following up Rubin Observatory's Legacy Survey of Space and Time, but it has already served an important role in time-domain astronomy, for example by searching for optical counterparts of gravitational wave events. Flexible scheduling and inter-telescope cooperation are important aspects of an efficient system for following up astronomical events, and the [AEON project](#), which enables these features, as was described by Cesar Briceño during the workshop.

Arjun Dey presented on "The NOIRLab 4m Telescopes and Their Future." This was followed by a round-the-room discussion with DOE and NSF senior personnel, and various NOIRLab directors, on Zoom. This was an animated discussion, and such discussions and planning for the future will continue.

This still image combines hundreds of time-lapse exposures that capture the entirety of the 8 November 2022 [total lunar eclipse](#) above the [Nicholas U. Mayall 4-meter Telescope](#) at [Kitt Peak National Observatory](#), a Program of NSF's NOIRLab. The image release can be [found here](#).

Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/P. Horálek (Institute of Physics in Opava)